

SOCIO-POLITICAL TRANSFORMATIONS AND THEIR CONSEQUENCES (1986-1990)

Abdullayev Baxromjon Khoshimjonovich

Senior teacher, department of history of world, Andijan state
university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6242830>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2022

Accepted: 10th February 2022

Online: 15th February 2022

KEY WORDS

Reconstruction, Socialism, Ideological unity, Communist party, Capitalism, sovereignty paradigm, Administrative and command methods, Totalitarian regimes, Political life, CIS.

Introduction. The restructuring policy and reforms implemented by the Soviet Communist Party (CPSU) between the 80s of the 20th century entered all aspects of socio-political life in Uzbekistan. At that time some of the democratic changes were made as a result of the implementation of this policy announced by the Secretary General of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Socialist Republic M. Gorbachev: party censorship weakened, citizens were allowed to express their opinion freely and independently, the media was liberalized. Particular attention was given to transparency (1). As a result, prominent intellectuals-writers and poets have begun to strike strongly against the communist ideology in their coverage. The former Soviet socialist system was sharply

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the socio-political situation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the eve of achieving the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1986-1990), the policy of the USSR government and the Communist Party's policy of tyranny towards Uzbekistan. The article also analyzes the socio-political and economic situation in Uzbekistan for the independence of Uzbekistan.

criticized throughout the Soviet Union. Particularly, all the errors of party and state leaders, the process of administrative manipulation, repression of the country's original children. In the long run, this was seen as an ideological factor in the collapse of the Union. However, the democratic values emerging in Moscow and other Russian cities- fierce criticism of the old system, such as transparency, have come to Uzbekistan without any trace. The "democracy" creators in the center treated the allied republics as patriarchal societies. For example, the process of "reconstruction of the old system as a result of centralized criticism campaigns started but in the Central Asian and regime is still living as it used to be", reflecting the views of the party elite at that time. In the central USSR mass media, there is a large number of

“additions” in cotton production in Uzbekistan, “corrupt practices” of most officials, in crease “bribery” as well as the allegations of slander, as well as the support of the party’s leadership in Moscow, the socio-political situation in the republic. In other words, the campaign of discrimination, which has not yet had its own socio-political foundation, has been regarded as a “sanction of punishment” for Uzbekistan. Traditionally, the party and the government of the USSR have traditionally been sent to Uzbekistan by officers of the Prime Minister’s Office, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and State security committee. The results of their weekly and monthly investigation have begun to be published in the media by the “ala”. In the short term, Uzbekistan has become a symbol of "corruption" among other USSR republics (2). From 1983 to 1989, as a result of the “trace” from the center, 60% of the heads of state-owned collective farms and state farmers, nearly 45% of leading agricultural specialists, and one third of all heads of cottonbreeding bureaucrats were removed from their posts. About 40,000 civilians who were working in that office were tortured by investigators from the center. They were kept in detention facilities during the investigations, and their polygamy was sent to prisons and Siberian camps. This situation dropped the spirit of the Uzbek people. The mood of the country has grown, the lack of trust in the future, social depression, and passivity have become one of the peculiarities of that time. Of course, during the same period in other republics of the USSR campaigns were started to disclose various "crimes". However, the "cotton case" in Uzbekistan was declared as

the most extreme crime in the whole union. Investigation into the "cotton case" has become a criminal "bestseller". By the second half of the 20th century, it began to be described as "the work of the Uzbeks." Television screens featured gold, gold coins and other precious items and sacks found in senior officials. The scale of this press attack was behind the planned implementation of the "general director" of the campaign as the leadership of the KPSS. Because at that time the center was unprecedented - 6 mln. tons of raw cotton, as a result of lack of opportunities to grow cotton in this amount, there was a political, social and economic crisis in the country. It was the centerpiece of the "cotton business" and "the case of the Uzbeks" in order to put pressure on the Uzbek leadership and to minimize the tension between the CPSU and the leadership of the Soviet state in Uzbekistan. The KPSS was rumors that the Uzbek population was "rich" to justify their repressive policies. The use of "cotton business" and "the work of the Uzbeks" in relation to an entire Uzbek nation, the promotion of the Uzbek people as a "negative image" of the whole union was not just social or legal injustice, but also a slander against an entire nation. It was no secret that during this period, the Soviet Union had been extending its influence to all the nations of the USSR in order to demonstrate the superiority of the socialist system in the Soviet Union, and that such cases were common to all the allied republics, even to the Russian republic. Therefore, similar campaigns in Uzbekistan have formed a negative attitude towards the Uzbek nation against the CPSU, the USSR. The people of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who have no innocent "evil",

began to form a tendency toward nationalism and national values. By the end of the 80's of the 20th century, as a result of the policy pursued by the people not only by the government, but also by the national interests that contradicted the colonial policy of the center, historic, political and economic conditions were being established to achieve the independence of Uzbekistan.

The "rebuilding" reforms announced by the center were initially implemented in the political sphere. The economic sphere was again politically governed by the previous one. As a result of ignoring the laws of economic development and transforming it into an appendix of the communist ideology, the balance between the national economy and the sociopolitical life has been disrupted and as a result, there are problems with the state and local government. This situation has aggravated people's living conditions (3). The "reconstruction" reforms announced by the center were not supported by the people with economic difficulties; on the other hand, governance in the provinces, cities and districts was largely owned by local party organizations, and they also slowed down the deepening of reforms on the ground. After all, party organizations in the areas did not have the confidence that the reforms would have a positive effect. In Uzbekistan, which was a part of the Soviet Union at that time, the policy of "restructuring" was still under way. The tragedy of the 'restructuring' policy was that while the ruling party was in the hands of the party, it had begun to reform the representative bodies and self-governing bodies before rebuilding the party. To this end, the representative bodies sought to

democratize the electoral system and improve the selection of candidates for the people's representation. The election of the first secretaries of the provincial, municipal and district party organizations as chairmen of the relevant representative bodies has further aggravated political life. Because party leaders, who are not yet experienced by the representative bodies of the representative bodies, consider themselves the leader of the party organization, rather than the representative body. They sometimes did not have the power to govern and make decisions based on regular dialogue and debate with a parliamentary team that reminded them of street protests. Moreover, it was easy to manage the party organizations. Because, thousands of organizational organizations and their monthly salaried secretaries in each district and city were subordinate to the high party organizations on the basis of "democratic centralism." Similarly, enterprises, institutions, and educational institutions prefer to be in the hands of higher party bodies than the representative of the sentiments to the sentence, trying to keep their work teams stable. Also, on June 21, 1987, the election process for local representative bodies did not produce the expected results. In the first place, democratic principles were not included in the election process, as the party's organizations were weakened by the fact that the predominance of the majority of voters was prevalent in the pre-election campaign. As a result of the elections to local councils held in Uzbekistan, 106484 deputies were elected, 37709 (35.7%) workers and 29209 (27.7%) representatives of collective.

The majority of MPs represent Slavic nationalities and the majority of deputies in the large industrial enterprises due to the fact that the contribution of local minorities to the minority (more than 70% of the population of the republic was ethnic Uzbek, only 45.7% representatives of other Russian-speaking peoples. In 1987, there were more than 642,000 party members in the Republican Party organization, representing 3.3% of the country's population. According to the results of the elections 105,494 deputies were elected, of which 44.6% were members of the party. The remaining 96.7 5 of the members of the population were only 55.4% (58448). These results have shown that the influence of the Communist Party in Uzbekistan still remains. The "restructuring" policy was sought to reform the system of elections to the supreme councils and local representative bodies of all USSR republics. In practice, however, the form of elections was changed furiously, but their essence and significance remained unchanged. In February and April 1990, elections to the Supreme Soviet of multi-mandate constituencies were held in Uzbekistan. This election was held under the monopoly of the Communist Party. The outcome of the election and its results were aimed at a great deal of silence on the country's economic and political reforms, but its results did not bring any public-political stability. The main focus was on promoting the declarative character of the election. For example, in most constituencies, candidates were alternatively nominated (174 alternate candidates from 50 single mandate constituencies were not nominated). Therefore, according to the

results of the elections, the number of workers, collective farmers, women and youth fell sharply among the deputies. Approximately 95 percent of the elected deputies were Communists (4). Because all the sub-organizations of the party interfered with the electoral process and took all possible measures to be taken to select the candidates they wanted. While the democratic transformation of the "Reconstruction" period was characteristic of the declarative nature, the multiplicity and mass rallies and meetings, as well as the rise of some informal organizations, resulted in the problems that have been accumulated during the period of the totalitarianism of the 1970s, which are characterized by the signs of socio-political crises went out. Moreover, as a result of the USSR's failure to comply with its contractual obligations to Uzbekistan by other USSR importers - such as sugar, confectionery products, cereal products, clothing, oil products, and spare parts for machinery - became ridiculous for various informal organizations. In 1989-1990, inter-ethnic conflicts and clashes took place in Fergana region, Parkent district of Tashkent region and Andizhan. These events were published in the press in line with the will of the center throughout the Soviet Union. The socio-political situation in the republic has aggravated. The causes of conflicts and clashes have been accumulated for many years in the pursuit of social feelings, economic depression, moral instability, and feelings of selfishness through the mobility of people who have lived under the slavery of a monotone for many years. On May 24, 1989, in Kuvasai, a form of "interethnic" ethnic tensions between the local youth and the young

Meskhetian Turks came to an end. The collapse spread throughout the Fergana Valley as a result of the lack of impartial information about the conflict, learning by the authorities of "socialist stability" that they suddenly experienced these events, the skill of leaders and their pursuit of events. The clashes soon spread to the residents of Fergana, Margilan, Toshbol, Kokand, Andizhan, Namangan and Tashkent, leading to mass demonstrations of young people and to other ethnic conflicts (5). With the consent of the center, which was afraid of such protests, local leaders brought military units against demonstrators. On June 8, 1989 in Kokand, more than 50 demonstrators were killed and more than 200 demonstrators were wounded in a shootout by military men, mostly young men. Also, as a result of the firing of militants from other regions of Ferghana region on June 3-1, 1989, 103 people were killed, of which 1009 were injured. The houses and yards of 650 families were burned and destroyed (6). The tragic events in Ferghana and other cities have proven that the local party, the Soviet and the public organizations were separated from the people, completely passionate about the suffering and the interests of the people, and that the social

sphere was abandoned. Meanwhile, the Government of the Republic has identified the following measures: elimination of cotton monopoly, stabilization of its cotton planting and cotton processing, revision of additional fees for cotton harvesting and cost of raw cotton, social protection of the poor, expansion of subsidiary farms and their lands, as well as implementation of measures that play an important role in eliminating the economic, social and political crisis in the other republic. As you can see from the analysis, all the political, social, and economic situations in which Uzbekistan gained independence were formed. The Uzbek nation and the government of the republic have united the interests of independence. In 1990, the government began to establish legal and economic foundations for achieving independence. On June 18, 1990 the 2nd session of the Supreme Soviet (Parliament) of the Republic adopted the Declaration of Independence (7). The adoption of this declaration without leaving the USSR was a turning point in the political life of the republic. The Declaration of Independence was a legal basis for proclaiming the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan proclaimed on 31 August 1991.

References

1. Look through: The social development of the Soviet society//[http:// histrel.ru/history of great country/a new_era/The social_development_ of the Soviet society htm](http://histrel.ru/history_of_great_country/a_new_era/The_social_development_of_the_Soviet_society.htm).
2. Socio-economical life of Uzbekistan in 1950-1990s.The emergency of crisis life////<http://vek-noviy.ru/istoriya-uzbekistana-1917-1991-g/sotsialno-ekonomicheskaya-zhizn-uzbekistana-v-1950-1990-g.html>.
3. Look through: Restructuring policy and its deficit//<http://vek-noviy.ru/istoriya-uzbekistana-1917-1991-g/Uzbekistan-na-puti-k-nezavizimosti.html>.
4. Uzbekistan in the years of perestroika // http://www.pr-j.ru/istoriya/uzbekistan_v_gody_perestrojki.html.

5. Chronicle of the life of nationalities on the eve of the collapse of the USSR. 1989 M. CIMO, 1994. p. 166
6. Osipov A.G. Fergana Valley: ethnicity, ethnic processes, ethnic conflicts. -M.: Science, 2004.-C.11-15.
7. Kirgizboev M. // <http://huquqburch.uz/uz/view/510>.